

**Gd+GdZn biphasic magnetic composites synthesized in a single preparation step:
increasing refrigerant capacity without decreasing magnetic entropy change.**

Jia Yan Law^{1,2}, Luis M. Moreno-Ramírez¹, Javier S. Blázquez¹, Victorino Franco^{1,1}, Alejandro Conde¹

¹Dpto. Física de la Materia Condensada, ICMSE-CSIC, Universidad de Sevilla, P.O. Box 1065, 41080, Sevilla, Spain

²Division of Permanent Magnets and Applications, IMDEA Nanoscience, Campus Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, 28049 Madrid, Spain

Abstract

Biphasic Gd+GdZn composites ($\text{Gd}_{(50+x)}\text{Zn}_{(50-x)}$; $x=0, 5, 15$ and 25 at.%) were successfully obtained in a single fabrication step by induction melting. X-ray microdiffraction results reveal the homogeneity of all the prepared samples and indicate a combination of GdZn and Gd phases with different proportions. With this method, the main drawbacks of preparing composites had been avoided, providing the additional advantage of enhanced thermal conductivity between phases. The biphasic Gd+GdZn composite had positively demonstrated an enhanced refrigerant capacity in comparison to Gd (11%) as well as to single phase GdZn (45%). Heat capacity measurements provide an adiabatic temperature change of around 3.5 K for 20 kOe for the optimal composite.

Keywords: Magnetocaloric effect; composites

¹ Corresponding author: vfranco@us.es

Introduction

Magnetic refrigeration, based on the magnetocaloric effect (MCE), has been widely classified as an emergent cooling technology with environment amity and good energy efficiency¹. In general, single phase magnetocaloric materials exhibit a peak in the entropy change close to the transition temperature, which can be particularly abrupt for first order phase transitions. However, in some thermodynamic refrigeration cycles, such as Ericsson-cycle, it would be beneficial to reduce the variation of the magnetic entropy values ($\Delta S_M(T)$) in a range of about 30 K to approach a table-like MCE (a constant ΔS_M in the refrigeration temperature range). This can be indirectly characterized using the refrigerant capacity (RC). Basically, the enhancement of RC requires a broad $\Delta S_M(T)$ with a large peak value of magnetic entropy change (ΔS_M^{pk}). However, it is challenging to find these two features for a single-phased magnetocaloric material. Care has to be taken when claiming of a large RC but corresponding to very low ΔS_M values, as it would be impossible to exploit these values in experimental devices. Thus, a realistic approach to optimize RC is the development of a two- or multi-phase magnetocaloric material with the appropriate selection of magnetic phase transition temperatures². Magnetocaloric composites have been both theoretically and experimentally shown to exhibit enhanced RC in comparison to pure phases². However, multiphase magnetocaloric materials are typically reported with relatively small ΔS_M^{pk} values³⁻⁶. Nevertheless, to be realistically applicable in devices, it is essential that each of the existing phases in the composite presents a large magnetocaloric response. Moreover, the typical approach to combine different phases in MCE composites, to date, involves the preparation of multilayers, mixing powders etc. However, these methods entail drawbacks, such as poor thermal conductivity between surfaces, additional time-consuming preparation steps during the synthesis, etc.

The binary GdZn intermetallic, whose Curie temperature (T_C) lies near room temperature, could co-exist with Gd phase^{pk} in a composite alloy by varying the Gd:Zn ratio, as according to its phase diagram⁷. As Gd is the reference magnetocaloric material near room temperature, it is of keen interest to study the MCE of the two-phase (Gd and GdZn) composite material. Theoretical predictions of the two-phase alloy showed that magnetocaloric properties are tuned by compositional varying of Gd:Zn ratio, which

could enable flexibility in the choice of thermodynamic cycle and highly effective MCE composite regenerator materials⁸. Despite the promising results from the theoretical MCE predictions of Gd+GdZn composite, no systematic studies of the composite were reported but the MCE of pure GdZn phase alloy instead⁸. Other relevant literature reports the MCE of several Gd eutectic compositions, which included Gd-GdZn but receiving the least focus^{9,10}. In addition, the synthesis routes of fabricating these composites were challenging and implying several steps and sophisticated manipulation⁸⁻¹⁰.

Hence, in this work, we aim to use an alternative approach to develop, in a single fabrication step, a material with mixed constituent phases within the composite (Gd+GdZn) with large magnetocaloric response.

Experimental

The Gd-Zn alloy series, with nominal composition of $Gd_{(50+x)}Zn_{(50-x)}$ (with $x = 0, 5, 15$ and 25 at.%), was prepared by induction melting in argon a stoichiometric mixture of pure Gd and Zn in a quartz crucible. Both commercial Gd and Zn are 99.9 and 99.98 wt.% pure, respectively. Besides pure Gd, the alloys are denoted by their Zn content as Zn50, Zn45, Zn35 and Zn25. A vacuum of 10^{-5} torr was obtained in the induction-melting furnace prior to filling the furnace with Ar gas to 700 mbar. The alloy (total weight of ~5 g) was melted 2 times to ensure homogeneity. Their microstructure and phases were characterized by X-ray microdiffraction (XRMD). The magnetic and heat capacity properties were measured using a commercial Physical Property Measurement System from Quantum Design in the temperature range of 220-380 K for magnetic fields up to 20 kOe. The ΔS_M of the alloys was determined from the $M-H$ isotherms using the Maxwell relation $\Delta S_M = \mu_o \int_0^H (\partial M / \partial T)_H dH$, where μ_o is the magnetic permeability of vacuum, H is the applied magnetic field, M is the magnetization and T is the temperature. RC is calculated using two methods: (a) RC_{FWHM} : the product of ΔS_M^{pk} and the full temperature width at half maximum of the peak ($RC_{FWHM} = \Delta S_M^{pk} \cdot \delta T_{FWHM}$), and (b) RC_{AREA} : numerical integration of the area under the $\Delta S_M(T)$ curves, using the full temperature width at half maximum of the peak as the integration limits. The adiabatic temperature change (ΔT_{ad}) has been calculated as:

$$\Delta T_{ad}(H) = [T_H(S) - T_0(S)]_S \quad (1)$$

where $T_H(S)$ curves were obtained from heat capacity measurements at constant pressure and magnetic field ($C_{P,H}$) using that $S(T, H) \cong \int_0^T \frac{C_{P,H}(T)}{T} dT$ (where the entropy at zero temperature is neglected)¹¹. Results are compared with the widely used method that neglects the field dependence of $C_{P,H}$, thus ΔT_{ad} can be approximated as¹²:

$$\Delta T_{ad}(H) \cong \frac{T}{C_{P,H}} \Delta S_M \quad (2)$$

To check the validity of the approximation, $C_{P,H}$ has been considered for the extremal cases $H=0$ and $H=20$ kOe.

Results and discussion

The experimental XRD patterns of the alloys are presented in **Figure 1** along with the corresponding theoretical ones and the individual contribution of each phase used in the fitting. Rietveld refinement analysis reveals 100% GdZn (CsCl-type) phase for Zn50 alloy, indicating the successful synthesis preparation method. For the rest of alloys, an amount of $\sim 4e8$ wt.% Gd_2O_3 impurity phase in addition to Gd and GdZn phases were detected, which suggests surface oxidation of the alloy as a likely scenario since Gd is easily susceptible to oxidation. The refinement results also showed increasing GdZn phase content with Zn concentration, which is in good agreement with the nominal composition.

Figure 1. X-ray microdiffraction patterns of $Gd_{50-x}Zn_{50-x}$ alloys. The Rietveld fitting along with the contribution of each individual phase are also shown.

The $\Delta S_M(T)$ curves of the alloys under an applied magnetic field of 20 kOe is presented in **Figure 2**. It is observed that only one ΔS_M^{pk} value was observed for single-phase alloys (Gd and Zn50 alloy) while a more table-like behavior (two ΔS_M^{pk} values at 265 ± 1 K and 290 ± 1 K) was obtained for biphasic alloys. In addition, all the ΔS_M^{pk} values occur at temperatures near room temperature and show very similar values (3.2 ± 0.2 J kg⁻¹K⁻¹). In the case of GdZn, the ΔS_M^{pk} (3.22 J kg⁻¹K⁻¹) of the alloy displays $\sim 70\%$ of that observed for pure Gd piece.

Figure 2. Temperature dependence of magnetic entropy change calculated from magnetization data for pure Gd and Gd+GdZn composites. Inset: compositional dependence of RC parameters for pure Gd and Gd+GdZn composites.

The compositional dependence of RC of the Gd-Zn alloys ($\Delta H=20$ kOe) is presented in inset of **Figure 2**. An 11% and 45% enhancement of RC was attained by the composites as compared to pure Gd and GdZn alloy, respectively, which could be attributed to the relatively small separation of the magnetic entropy change peaks of the two phases (i.e. 266-290 K), which gives rise to the table-like shape of $\Delta S_M(T)$ curves. The large temperature range of the maximum MCE properties, 266-290 K, facilitated these composites with good flexibility in adjusting the temperature dependencies of ΔS_M , which is accessible from the tuning of Gd:Zn ratio. This enables the composites as potential candidate materials for different magnetic refrigeration cycles and thus different cooling applications. It is worth noting that the separation between peaks cannot be arbitrarily chosen in a composite, as too large distance will decrease RC , while too close peaks would cause no improvement². The improvement of the table-like

character of $\Delta S_M(T)$ curves can be estimated as the dispersion, $\sigma(\Delta S_M)$, of these values around the average one, $\langle \Delta S_M \rangle$, in a certain temperature span, ΔT . Using $\Delta T = 30$ K, the flatness, defined as $f = 100 \frac{\sigma(\Delta S_M)}{\Delta S_M}$ with lower f values corresponding to a more table-like behavior, reduces from 16% and 13% for pure Gd and GdZn phases, respectively, to less than 6% for Zn25 alloy.

Assuming a non-interacting phases model for Gd+GdZn biphasic alloy, the total magnetic entropy change of a sample with a fraction y of GdZn phase is $\Delta S_M = (1-y) \Delta S_M(\text{Gd}) + y \Delta S_M(\text{GdZn})$. Therefore, the quantitative mass fractions of each phase could be deconvoluted from the experimental $\Delta S_M(T)$ curves¹³, as shown in **Figure 3**. The results show that the composites are well represented by this model. The phase analysis calculated from the XRMD and MCE data show good agreement with the nominal composition of the Gd-Zn alloys, as seen in **Figure 3 (d)** **Error! Reference source not found.** This indicates that this single step synthesis method is capable of producing samples with Gd+GdZn phases, allowing full integration of Zn in GdZn phase.

Figure 3. Calculation of mass phase fractions of Gd and GdZn in $\text{Gd}_{50-x}\text{Zn}_{50-x}$ alloys from MCE results: (a) Zn45, (b) Zn35 and (c) Zn25 alloys. (d) Estimated Zn content in Gd-Zn alloy series from XRMD and MCE results.

The C_p curves ($H=0, 10$ and 20 kOe) for the studied composites are presented in **Figure 4 (a)**. For zero applied field, abrupt transition peaks are observed. These distinct peaks become smoother and eventually merge with higher magnetic fields. Moreover, $C_{p,H}$ curves show the largest field dependence for relatively small applied fields and temperatures around the transition temperatures. Based on **eq. (1)**, ΔT_{ad} curves calculated from $C_{p,H}$ data, reveal maximum values of 3.5 K ($H=20$ kOe) for the optimal composite (as shown in **Figure 4(b)**). The calculated ΔT_{ad} curves ($H=0, 20$ kOe) using **eq. (2)** are shown in the inset of **Figure 4**, showing a good agreement of the different calculation methods (difference of $\sim 8\%$).

Figure 4. Heat capacity curves for 0, 10 and 20 kOe for the composites (a). Derived adiabatic temperature change at 20 kOe (b). Inset: ΔT_{ad} curves from different approximations for $\text{Gd}_{50}\text{Zn}_{50}$ alloy.

Conclusions

The magnetocaloric composites of Gd+GdZn experimentally obtained in this work are offered as a good strategy to improve RC and have a table-like MCE, which could be appropriate for Ericsson-type refrigeration cycles. They exhibited relatively constant ΔS_M^{pk} for 25 – 50 at.% Zn content. The biphasic alloy demonstrated an enhanced RC as compared to the reference MCE material, Gd (11%), as well as to single phase GdZn (45%). The MCE results of Gd+GdZn composites could be modelled by considering non-interacting phases. An adiabatic temperature change of 3.5 K for 20 kOe has been

obtained for the optimal composite from heat capacity measurements using different calculation methods. The feasibility of preparing these composites in a single step, in addition to reducing material costs, enables the fabrication of a bulk material. This provides advantages over other composites, like simpler preparation method and improved thermal contact between phases. The selected phases prevent the significant loss of ΔS_M^{pk} usually associated to an enhanced RC.

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